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Supplementary Information for*

***Identification of Miocene Maiga olivine leucitites in southern Tibet: Implication for the presence of
hidden carbonated mantle reservoir***

Ming Lei^{a,b}, Jianlin Chen^{a,b}, Jifeng Xu^c, Zhiqiang Kang^d, Zhihui Cheng^e*

*a State Key Laboratory of Isotope Geochemistry, Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Guangzhou 510640,
China*

b CAS Centre for Excellence in Deep Earth Sciences, Guangzhou 510640, China

*c State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources, School of Earth Science and Resources, China University of
Geosciences, Beijing 100083, China*

d Guangxi Key Laboratory of Hidden Metallic Ore Deposits Exploration, Guilin University of Technology, Guilin 541004, China

e School of Geographical Science, Lingnan Normal University, Zhanjiang 524048, China

**Corresponding author: Prof. Jianlin Chen*

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Introduction:

The supporting information provides the evidence for analytical methods ([Supplementary text 1](#)); mineral map (a) and photomicrograph (b) of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Fig. 1](#)); diagrams of En–Wo–Fs clinopyroxene classification (a) and clinopyroxene O isotopes (b) of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Fig. 2](#)); diagrams of (a) CaO (wt.%) versus MgO (wt.%), (b) FeOT/MnO versus MgO (wt.%), and (c) FeOT/CaO-3MgO/SiO₂ versus MgO (wt.%) of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Fig. 3](#)); Ar-Ar aging data of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Table 1](#)); major compositions, O isotopes, and H₂O content data of clinopyroxene of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Table 2](#)); and whole-rock major-trace elements and Sr-Nd-Pb-Hf-Zn isotope data of the Maiga olivine leucitites ([Supplementary Table 3](#)).

Supplementary text 1: analytical methods.

1. TIMA mineral map analysis

The MIRA3 scanning electron microscope at the Guangzhou Tuoyan Analytical Technology Co., Ltd, Guangzhou, China was used to map the mineral composition on carbon-coated thin sections (mounts). During the analysis, a probe current of 8.24 nA, an acceleration voltage of 25 kV, and 15 mm working distance were chosen. The dot spacing was set to 9 μ m, and the pixel spacing was 3 μ m. Using the automated process, the current and BSE signal intensity were calibrated on a platinum Faraday cup. Using the manganese standard, EDS performance was evaluated. The TIMA liberation analysis program was used to scan the samples.

2. Ar–Ar dating

$^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating was performed using the a GV5400 Ar–Ar mass spectrometer Guangzhou Institute of Geochemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences (GIGCAS)., Guangzhou, China. Argon gas was extracted from the sample by step-heating using an MIR10 CO₂ continuous laser. The released gases were purified using Ti and Al–Zr getters pumps, and 5-8 min was allowed for equilibration before conducting a static analysis. The $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating results were calculated and plotted using the computer program ISOPLOT v3.0. The J-value was estimated by replicate

analyse of Fish Canyon Tuff sanidine (27.55 ± 0.08 Ma) and the ZBH biotite (133.3 ± 0.24 Ma) standard. The detailed experimental procedure is provided in [Qiu & Jiang \(2007\)](#).

3. Major compositions of clinopyroxene (Cpx)

Major elements of olivine were carried out using a JEOL JXA-iSP-100 Electron Probe Microanalyzer equipped with five wavelength-dispersive spectrometers at the Laboratory of Guangzhou Tuoyan Analytical Technology Co., Ltd. The main operating conditions of instrumental analysis include the accelerating voltage of 15 kV, a beam current of 10 nA, and 5 μm spot size. The peak counting time was 10 s for Mg and Si, and 20 s for Al, Ni, Fe, Ca and Mn. The data reduction was performed via the atomic number absorption-fluorescence (ZAF) correction procedure. The precision of Cpx major elements is better than 5%.

4. Oxygen isotope of clinopyroxene (Cpx)

Oxygen isotope composition of Cpx were measured using the CAMECA IMS 1280-HR SIMS at GIG-CAS. The Cs⁺ primary beam was accelerated at 10 kV with an intensity of ca. 2 nA. The spot size was about 10 × 20 μm. A normal incidence electron flood gun was activated to compensate for sample charging during analysis. Mass resolution of ca. 2500 was obtained with multi-collection mode. A nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) controller was used for the magnetic field. The signals of ¹⁶O and ¹⁸O were collected simultaneously using two Faraday cups and were amplified by circuits employing 1010 Ω and 1011 Ω resistance, respectively. Each analysis consisted of 20 cycles × 4 s counting time. Typical ion intensities of 2–4 × 10⁶ counts per second obtained on the ¹⁸O peak yielded an internal 2σ uncertainty of better than ±0.2‰. Three standard δ¹⁸O measurements were run in bracketed mode. The external reproducibility of the standard (06JY31-cpx) for δ¹⁸O was 0.2‰ (2σ), which was set as the error for individual measurements. Measured ¹⁸O/¹⁶O ratios are reported as δ¹⁸O per mil (‰) values calculated relative to oxygen isotopic composition of Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water (¹⁸O/¹⁶O)_{VSMOW} = 0.0020052 and then corrected for instrumental mass fractionation (IMF). Then the δ¹⁸O for samples were corrected by the equation: δ¹⁸O_{sample} = δ¹⁸O_{measured} + IMF. Given that the impact of instrumental mass fractionation (IMF) of SIMS oxygen isotope analysis of Cpx with Fo number >80 is negligible (Tang et al., 2019) and Cpx grains of Maiga Olivine Leucitites have high and homogeneous Fo number (90–92), the potential IMF effect on the measured O isotopes values was not considered. The detailed measurement of Cpx O isotopes is described by Tang et al. (2019).

5. Water content of clinopyroxene (Cpx)

The SIMS water content measurements were carried out by using a CAMECA IMS 1280-HR at GIGCAS. A Cs⁺ primary beam of 3nA and with the spot size of 15 mm was used to sputter secondary ions from the samples with an impact energy of 20 kV. A normal-incidence electron gun (NEG) was used to ensure a charged compensation throughout the measurement sessions. A nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) controller was used for the magnetic field. The field aperture, contrast aperture, entrance slit and max area were set at 2000, 400, ~ 60, and ~ 80 mm. The energy slit was set to be 50 eV with a 5 eV gap. Two Faraday cup detectors with resistors of 1010 Ohm and 1011 Ohm, and an electron multiplier of mono-collector were used to simultaneously collect ¹⁶O⁻, ¹⁸O⁻, and ¹⁶O1H⁻, respectively. The total analytical time of every point is about 4.5 minutes. The precision of measured H₂O values of standard 06JY3 is generally better than 10%. The reference materials (KLB; BOU; 06JY31; PR-7-2; SLP-108 SLP-101; KH03-4; and SC-J1) are used to establish the calibration line and the detailed H₂O measurement of Cpx can be found in [Zhang et al. \(2023\)](#).

6. Whole-rock major-trace element and Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb-Zn analyses

Whole-rock major-trace elements and Sr-Nd isotopes were performed at GIGCAS. Whole-rock Hf-Pb-Zn isotopes were conducted at Wuhan sample solution Analytical Technology Co. Ltd., Wuhan, China.

Whole-rock major elements were analyzed by using a X-ray fluorescence spectrometer on glass disks by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF). A pre-ignition procedure was used to determine the loss on ignition (LOI) prior to major element analyse and the analytical precision was generally better than 5% based on the measurement of Chinese rock standard (GSR-1, GSR-2 and GSR-3). Whole-rock trace elements were obtained by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Sample powders (~50 mg) were digested using a HF + HNO₃ mixture in Teflon vessels, which were heated to 190 °C in an oven for over 24 h. The USGS rock standards BHVO-2 and AGV-1 were run as unknown to monitor the data quality. The precision of rare earth elements (REEs) and high field strength elements (HFSEs) analyse is generally better than 10%. The trace elements of USGS reference (BHVO-2 and AGV-1) in this study are provided below, which are in good agreement with the reference values within the analytical errors.

For whole-rock Sr–Nd isotopic analysis, sample powders were dissolved in HF–HClO₄, and the dissolution was conducted at 200 °C for seven days. Sr and Nd were separated using conventional ion exchange columns, and the Nd fractions were further separated with di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (HDEHP)-coated Kef columns. Whole-rock Sr–Nd isotopic compositions were measured using a Multi-Collector Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (MC-ICPMS). During the data acquisition, the measured ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr ratio of NBS987 and ¹⁴³Nd/¹⁴⁴Nd ratio of JNdi-1 were 0.710288 ± 28 (2σ , $n = 9$), and 0.512109 ± 12 (2σ , $n = 8$), respectively. The measured Sr and Nd isotopic ratios were normalized to $^{86}\text{Sr}/^{88}\text{Sr} = 0.1194$, and $^{146}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd} = 0.7219$, respectively. The Sr–Nd isotopic ratios of USGS reference (BCR-2 and BHVO-2) in this study are provided below, which are in good agreement with the reference values within the analytical errors.

For whole-rock Pb isotopic analysis, sample powders in the Teflon beakers were spiked and dissolved in concentrated HF at the temperature of 180 °C for 7 h. The Pb was separated via the cation-exchange technique with diluted HBr. The procedural blanks were 50 pg Pb. Pb isotopic analysis was measured by Neptune plus MC-ICP-MS. The measured Pb isotopic ratios were corrected for mass fractionation based on repeated analyses of international standard NBS981. During our analysis, the repeated analyses of SRM 981 yielded mean values of $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb} = 16.942 \pm 0.001$, $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb} = 15.500 \pm 0.001$ and $^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb} = 36.728 \pm 0.001$ (2σ , $n = 8$). The Pb isotopic ratios of USGS reference (BCR-2 and RGM-2) in this study are provided below, which are in good agreement with the reference values within the analytical errors.

For whole-rock Hf isotopic analysis, about 200 mg of sample powders were digested in Teflon bombs with a mixture of concentrated HNO₃ + HF and dried on a hot plate. This was followed by addition of concentrated HNO₃, HF and HClO₄ sealed in bombs and kept in an oven at 190 °C. After cooling, the Teflon bomb was opened and then 1 ml HNO₃ was added and evaporated to dryness. The Hf fraction was separated using a modified single-column separation procedure involving ion exchange with Ln-Spec resin. Hf isotopic analysis was measured by Neptune plus MC-ICP-MS. Mass discrimination correction was carried out via internal normalization to ¹⁷⁹Hf/¹⁷⁷Hf ratio of 0.7325. During our analysis, replicate measurements of the Alfa Hf standard during analysis gave an average ¹⁷⁶Hf/¹⁷⁷Hf ratio of 0.282224 ± 0.000007 (2σ, n =7). The Hf isotopic ratios of USGS reference (BCR-2 and RGM-2) in this study are given below, which are in good agreement with the reference values within the analytical errors.

For whole-rock Zn isotopic analysis, approximately 0.1g sample powders are mixed with 1ml concentrated HF and 1ml concentrated HNO₃ to be dissolved on hotplate at 120 °C for one day. Then, the solutions are dried down and an extra 1ml HNO₃ is introduced and evaporated. Subsequently, 1.5ml concentrated HCl and 0.5ml concentrated HNO₃ are added to the samples on a hotplate at 120°C for two days. After whole digestion, 1ml HCl is added and evaporated to dryness. Finally, the residual sample is dissolved in 1ml 8 N HCl and 0.001% H₂O₂ to prepare for chemical purification. Zinc fraction was collected in 10 ml 0.5 N HNO₃. The recovery for Zn is >99%. The detailed chemical purification is

described by [Zhu et al. \(2019\)](#). Zinc isotopic ratios were measured using the Neptune plus MC-ICP-MS. Standard-sample bracketing method was used to correct for instrumental mass fractionation. Zn isotopic data are reported in standard notation in per mil relative to standard reference material JMC Lyon standard.

$$\delta^{66}\text{Zn} = [({}^{66}\text{Zn}/{}^{64}\text{Zn})_{\text{Sample}}/({}^{66}\text{Zn}/{}^{64}\text{Zn})_{\text{JMC Lyon}} - 1] \times 1000$$

The long-term external reproducibility for $\delta^{66}\text{Zn}$ measurement is better than $\pm 0.05\text{‰}$ (2SD), based on repeated analyses of natural samples and synthetic solutions. The Zn isotopic ratios of USGS reference (BCR-2 and BHVO-2) in this study were provided below, which are in good agreement with the reference values within the analytical errors.

	BHVO-2	ref	AGV-1	ref
Sc	32.1	31.8	12.3	12.2
V	318	317	118	121
Cr	290	289	10.7	10.1
Co	44.8	45	15.6	15.3
Ni	119	121	16.2	16
Cu	135	136	56.2	60
Zn	108	105	85.9	88

Ga	21.3	21	20.5	20
Ge	1.68	1.64	1.09	1.25
Rb	10	11	69.2	67.3
Sr	398	403	659	662
Y	27.6	27.6	19.2	20
Zr	177	179	227	227
Nb	19.7	19	15.5	15
Cs	0.11	0.13	1.18	1.28
Ba	137	139	1236	1226
La	15.9	15.8	38.7	38
Ce	38.5	39	67.8	67
Pr	5.52	5.7	7.76	7.6
Nd	25.7	25.2	33.3	33
Sm	6.13	6.2	5.76	5.9
Eu	2.03	2.06	1.68	1.64
Gd	6.11	6.4	4.99	5
Td	0.98	0.96	0.69	0.7
Dy	5.22	5.2	3.6	3.6
Ho	1	0.99	0.68	0.67
Er	2.5	2.4	1.78	1.7
Tm	0.34	0.33	0.26	0.34
Yb	1.99	2.02	1.68	1.72
Lu	0.29	0.29	0.27	0.27
Hf	4.29	4.38	5.16	5.1
Ta	1.23	1.23	0.89	0.9

Pb	2.25	2.6	33.1	36
Th	1.18	1.08	6.38	6.5
U	0.4	0.42	1.88	1.92

	BHVO-2	Ref.	BCR-2	Ref.	RGM-2	Ref.
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	0.703481±3	0.70348 ±8	0.705012±8	0.705026 ± 20		
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.512979±2	0.512982±8	0.512633±6	0.512638 ± 15		
$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$			18.757	18.753 ±8	18.96	18.950±10
$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$			15.628	15.621 ± 4	15.623	15.618±2
$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$			38.735 ±1	38.725 ±22	38.671 ±1	38.660±8
$^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$			0.282870 ±9	0.282869 ±9	0.283023 ±9	0.283020±8
$\delta^{66}\text{Zn}$	0.32±0.04	0.31±0.03	0.26±0.03	0.26±0.03		

Note: values for the reference materials are from GeoREM (<http://georem.mpch-mainz.gwdg.de/>).

Supplementary Figure 1: mineral map (a) and photomicrograph (b) of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

Note: Ol, olivine; Cpx, clinopyroxene; Lut, leucite.

Supplementary Figure 2: diagrams of En–Wo–Fs clinopyroxene classification (a) and clinopyroxene O isotopes (b) of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

Note: The mantle Cpx $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value (5.5‰–6.0‰) is from Eiler (2001).

Fig. 3. Diagrams of (a) CaO (wt.%) versus MgO (wt.%), (b) FeOT/MnO versus MgO (wt.%), and (c) FeOT/CaO-3MgO/SiO₂ versus MgO (wt.%) of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

Note: The fields for peridotite- and pyroxenite-derived melts in a and b are from Herzberg et al. (2011); peridotite- and pyroxenite-derived melts in c are from Yang & Zhou (2013).

Supplementary Table 1: Ar-Ar data of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

	³⁶ Ar (a)	³⁷ Ar (ca)	³⁸ Ar (cl)	³⁹ Ar (k)	⁴⁰ Ar (r)	⁴⁰ Ar (r) (%)	³⁹ Ar (k) (%)	Age (Ma)	2σ
Sample 07MG-02 (whole-rock), J = 0.00415336 ± 0.00000208.									
GIG03CJLC23-S22	1.654968	3.659242	0.730578	278.0224	607.743	49.13	4.86	16.34	0.71
GIG03CJLC23-S25	2.029609	5.787314	1.119278	413.4456	904.848	53.96	7.23	16.36	0.59
GIG03CJLC23-S26	1.626951	5.108257	0.969136	350.2931	765.329	55.29	6.13	16.34	0.56
GIG03CJLC23-S27	1.702518	3.833212	0.987759	357.1886	794.198	55.09	6.25	16.62	0.58
GIG03CJLC23-S29	3.098317	8.851157	1.918908	712.1927	1569.900	57.12	12.46	16.48	0.53
GIG03CJLC23-S30	1.676771	3.537573	1.160370	441.4158	960.588	60.09	7.72	16.27	0.47
GIG03CJLC23-S31	1.565031	2.855177	1.229075	467.0618	1019.776	63.13	8.17	16.32	0.42
GIG03CJLC23-S33	1.606421	3.847716	1.203792	457.2528	997.498	62.01	8.00	16.31	0.44
GIG03CJLC23-S34	1.556808	2.800972	1.263404	462.1219	1014.054	63.12	8.09	16.41	0.42
GIG03CJLC23-S35	1.765251	4.402010	1.407845	532.8451	1196.374	64.04	9.32	16.79	0.42

Supplementary Table 2: major compositions, O isotopes, and H₂O content of clinopyroxene of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

	MG-07-02-01@01	MG-07-02-01@02	MG-07-02-01@03	MG-07-02-01@04	MG-07-02-01@05	MG-07-02-01@06	MG-07-02-01@08	MG-07-02-01@09	MG-07-02-01@10	MG-07-02-01@11	MG-07-02-01@13
SiO ₂	54.40	54.59	54.53	54.32	54.38	53.93	54.27	53.97	54.69	54.45	54.07
TiO ₂	0.26	0.25	0.26	0.25	0.24	0.28	0.22	0.32	0.21	0.18	0.26
Al ₂ O ₃	1.17	1.29	0.91	0.90	0.96	1.18	1.04	1.26	0.93	1.12	0.99
FeO	2.95	2.86	2.99	2.86	2.92	2.96	3.01	2.93	3.01	2.98	2.86
MnO	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.05
MgO	16.55	16.89	16.64	16.72	16.77	16.42	16.74	16.33	16.86	16.89	16.69
CaO	24.05	24.03	24.18	24.53	24.42	24.44	23.96	24.61	23.86	23.76	24.32
K ₂ O	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Mg#	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91
Total	99.80	100.42	99.83	100.03	100.15	99.70	99.72	100.01	100.04	99.95	99.62
En	46.6	47.2	46.6	46.5	46.6	46.0	46.9	45.8	47.2	47.3	46.6
Wo	48.6	48.2	48.6	49.0	48.7	49.2	48.2	49.6	48.0	47.8	48.8
Fs	4.8	4.6	4.8	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.9	4.7	4.8	4.9	4.6
^{iv} Al	0.0122	0.0203	0.0072	0.0191	0.0204	0.0262	0.0162	0.0299	0.0074	0.0169	0.0213
Ca	0.9414	0.9336	0.9467	0.9584	0.9523	0.9584	0.9384	0.9625	0.9313	0.9272	0.9536
D (H ₂ O)	0.0063	0.0067	0.0061	0.0065	0.0066	0.0068	0.0065	0.0070	0.0062	0.0066	0.0066
δ ¹⁸ O-Cpx	6.72	6.88	7.27	7.31	7.27	7.37	7.63	7.62	7.36	7.43	7.45
2SE	0.19	0.19	0.14	0.21	0.23	0.26	0.30	0.31	0.25	0.18	0.21
H ₂ O-Cpx	62.22	102.09	70.08	70.97	70.97	77.37	71.16	75.08	70.42	80.01	74.31
H ₂ O-melts	0.98	1.52	1.15	1.09	1.07	1.13	1.09	1.08	1.14	1.21	1.12

	MG-07-02-01@14	MG-07-02-01@15	MG-07-02-01@16	MG-07-02-01@18	MG-07-02-01@20	MG-07-02-01@22	MG-07-02-01@23	MG-07-02-01@24	MG-07-02-01@25	MG-07-04@01	MG-07-04@2
SiO ₂	54.28	54.97	54.58	54.70	54.37	54.37	54.53	54.41	54.60	54.42	53.93
TiO ₂	0.24	0.14	0.23	0.25	0.27	0.21	0.24	0.29	0.24	0.28	0.36
Al ₂ O ₃	1.17	0.95	0.92	1.02	0.95	0.99	1.43	0.99	1.22	0.91	1.29
FeO	2.95	2.97	2.90	3.05	3.09	3.07	3.13	3.04	2.89	2.78	2.73
MnO	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09
MgO	16.71	17.76	16.90	16.60	16.66	16.94	16.95	16.45	16.58	16.68	16.19
CaO	23.87	22.92	24.19	24.20	24.53	23.89	23.37	24.34	23.83	24.41	24.51
K ₂ O	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Mg#	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.92	0.91
Total	99.75	100.18	100.13	100.11	100.28	99.94	100.11	99.99	99.90	99.92	99.79
En	47.0	49.4	47.0	46.4	46.2	47.2	47.7	46.1	46.9	46.6	45.8
Wo	48.3	45.8	48.4	48.7	48.9	47.9	47.3	49.0	48.4	49.0	49.8
Fs	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.9	4.9	4.9	5.0	4.9	4.7	4.5	4.5
^{iv} Al	0.0171	0.0083	0.0136	0.0061	0.0212	0.0841	0.1217	0.0847	0.1056	0.0133	0.0257
Ca	0.9344	0.8899	0.9433	0.9451	0.9566	1.8493	1.8060	1.8876	1.8699	0.9546	0.9613
D (H ₂ O)	0.0066	0.0065	0.0064	0.0061	0.0066	0.0041	0.0054	0.0039	0.0046	0.0063	0.0068
δ ¹⁸ O-Cpx	7.86	7.76	7.83	7.69	7.59	7.61	7.72	7.45	7.86	7.20	7.46
2SE	0.20	0.18	0.26	0.14	0.26	0.22	0.28	0.20	0.24	0.21	0.24
H ₂ O-Cpx	77.69	74.11	69.01	78.85	65.13	66.33	64.65	60.61	61.12	83.47	81.79
H ₂ O-melts	1.18	1.14	1.08	1.30	0.98	1.63	1.19	1.54	1.33	1.33	1.21

	MG-07-04@03	MG-07-04@4	MG-07-04@5	MG-07-04@6	MG-07-04@7	MG-07-04@8	MG-07-06@01	MG-07-06@02	MG-07-06@03	MG-07-06@04	MG-07-06@05
SiO ₂	53.43	54.53	54.19	54.29	54.89	54.28	53.55	53.37	53.59	53.64	53.79
TiO ₂	0.45	0.30	0.28	0.30	0.26	0.28	0.27	0.24	0.33	0.27	0.29
Al ₂ O ₃	1.68	1.05	1.02	1.06	1.02	1.13	0.98	1.27	0.95	0.89	0.90
FeO	2.68	2.61	2.64	2.70	2.77	2.72	2.78	2.71	2.68	2.73	2.81
MnO	0.09	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.10	0.09	0.06
MgO	15.71	16.37	16.48	16.24	16.61	16.39	16.72	16.78	16.57	16.85	16.78
CaO	24.61	24.42	24.22	24.04	24.17	24.58	24.23	23.68	24.57	24.31	24.22
K ₂ O	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Mg#	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
Total	99.66	99.86	99.75	99.61	100.32	100.06	99.09	98.83	99.16	99.13	99.26
En	45.0	46.2	46.6	46.3	46.7	46.0	46.8	47.5	46.3	46.9	46.9
Wo	50.6	49.5	49.2	49.3	48.8	49.6	48.7	48.1	49.3	48.7	48.6
Fs	4.5	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.5
^{iv} Al	0.0381	0.0063	0.0166	0.0079	0.0030	0.0198	0.0304	0.0348	0.0294	0.0298	0.0255
Ca	0.9681	0.9564	0.9496	0.9453	0.9421	0.9608	0.9549	0.9343	0.9681	0.9568	0.9524
D (H ₂ O)	0.0073	0.0060	0.0065	0.0061	0.0060	0.0065	0.0070	0.0074	0.0069	0.0070	0.0068
δ ¹⁸ O-Cpx	7.71	7.95	3.92	7.39	8.23	8.38	8.20	8.01	8.12	8.00	7.95
2SE	0.26	0.20	0.19	0.24	0.26	0.24	0.22	0.30	0.54	0.29	0.21
H ₂ O-Cpx	80.12	89.90	89.61	95.75	84.38	81.47	60.59	55.73	64.33	58.10	58.84
H ₂ O-melts	1.09	1.50	1.39	1.56	1.42	1.25	0.86	0.75	0.93	0.83	0.86

	MG-07-06@06	MG-07-06@07	MG-07-06@09	MG-07-06@11	MG-07-06@12	MG-07-06@13	MG-07-06@14	MG-07-06@16	MG-07-06@17	MG-07-06@18	MG-07-06@19
SiO ₂	53.72	53.90	53.82	53.29	53.88	53.87	54.51	54.33	54.38	54.05	53.53
TiO ₂	0.24	0.24	0.21	0.33	0.24	0.27	0.19	0.20	0.16	0.27	0.27
Al ₂ O ₃	1.07	1.03	0.86	1.29	0.95	1.11	0.87	0.84	0.86	1.01	1.18
FeO	2.74	2.85	2.67	2.84	2.68	2.53	2.79	2.76	2.82	2.73	2.72
MnO	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.02	0.07
MgO	16.97	17.03	16.82	16.61	16.97	16.74	17.15	17.21	17.67	16.95	16.75
CaO	23.88	23.90	24.60	24.35	24.36	24.43	23.20	23.68	23.41	24.50	24.05
K ₂ O	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Mg#	0.92	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
Total	99.08	99.45	99.32	99.39	99.47	99.63	99.20	99.55	99.86	99.78	99.00
En	47.5	47.5	46.7	46.5	47.1	46.8	48.4	48.1	48.9	46.9	47.1
Wo	48.1	47.9	49.1	49.0	48.6	49.1	47.1	47.5	46.6	48.8	48.6
Fs	4.4	4.6	4.2	4.5	4.3	4.1	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.3	4.4
^{iv} Al	0.0276	0.0270	0.0270	0.0460	0.0284	0.0298	0.0013	0.0151	0.0221	0.0283	0.1008
Ca	0.9396	0.9374	0.9662	0.9566	0.9549	0.9573	0.9115	0.9268	0.9123	0.9577	1.8647
D (H ₂ O)	0.0070	0.0070	0.0068	0.0078	0.0069	0.0070	0.0061	0.0065	0.0070	0.0069	0.0045
δ ¹⁸ O-Cpx	8.06	8.73	7.69	8.49	8.21	8.23	8.59	8.04	7.98	8.36	8.37
2SE	0.34	0.30	0.22	0.42	0.26	0.20	0.26	0.22	0.20	0.29	0.26
H ₂ O-Cpx	57.35	61.63	59.09	61.93	66.74	60.85	59.82	107.86	107.61	60.50	60.07
H ₂ O-melts	0.82	0.88	0.87	0.80	0.96	0.87	0.98	1.65	1.55	0.87	1.34

	MG-07-06@20	MG-07-06@21
SiO ₂	53.95	53.67
TiO ₂	0.29	0.33
Al ₂ O ₃	0.90	0.95
FeO	2.72	2.67
MnO	0.06	0.07
MgO	17.05	16.69
CaO	24.39	24.35
K ₂ O	0.01	0.01
Mg#	0.92	0.92
Total	99.69	99.07
En	47.2	46.7
Wo	48.5	49.0
Fs	4.3	4.3
^{iv} Al	0.0765	0.0809
Ca	1.8811	1.8947
D (H ₂ O)	0.0038	0.0038
δ ¹⁸ O-Cpx	8.53	8.32
2SE	0.21	0.32
H ₂ O-Cpx	65.88	59.78
H ₂ O-melts	1.75	1.57

Supplementary Table 3: whole-rock major-trace elements, and Sr-Nd-Hf-Pb isotopes of the Maiga olivine leucitites.

	07MG-01	07MG-02	07MG-03	07MG-04	07MG-05	07MG-06	07MG-07
Major elements (wt.%)							
SiO ₂	45.66	46.33	45.07	45.23	45.62	44.62	45.21
TiO ₂	0.86	0.86	1.06	0.83	0.88	0.87	0.84
Al ₂ O ₃	9.16	9.47	9.10	9.26	9.47	9.17	9.17
Fe ₂ O ₃ T	8.11	8.31	8.07	7.90	8.13	8.06	8.04
MnO	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.13
MgO	14.67	14.46	13.98	15.18	14.51	15.42	15.74
CaO	11.14	10.32	10.14	9.63	10.46	10.21	9.68
Na ₂ O	0.81	1.36	1.76	1.33	1.04	1.01	1.24
K ₂ O	4.02	5.63	5.38	6.01	5.43	5.49	5.77
P ₂ O ₅	0.56	0.48	0.93	0.87	0.92	0.71	0.86
LOI	3.71	1.48	2.39	1.74	2.23	2.64	1.83
Total	98.84	98.84	98.03	98.11	98.81	98.34	98.51
Mg#	78.2	77.5	77.4	79.2	77.9	79.1	79.5
Trace elements (ppm)							
Sc	24.86	25.24	24.08	22.96	24.64	24.43	22.89
V	130.20	133.40	132.89	138.46	140.60	144.60	130.00
Cr	441.20	456.10	463.73	497.17	416.00	454.00	464.80
Co	43.52	46.09	45.68	48.26	45.31	48.14	48.82
Ni	359.30	397.90	386.77	460.42	386.70	455.00	499.10
Cu	70.71	59.28	57.16	66.24	65.32	69.53	75.37
Zn	84.08	82.82	85.06	87.01	87.70	86.64	84.73

Ga	13.16	13.73	14.18	14.13	14.09	14.15	13.62
Rb	290.50	290.90	288.41	321.68	292.40	292.20	291.70
Sr	2128.30	1995.40	1942.08	2601.24	3476.50	2925.60	3242.00
Y	35.65	34.61	36.70	37.42	35.41	38.50	33.83
Zr	292.50	294.90	288.44	299.82	303.50	325.90	299.10
Nb	10.00	10.67	11.71	11.60	10.90	12.17	10.24
Cs	26.20	26.77	25.26	27.94	24.95	24.40	26.31
Ba	13096.50	8535.00	7953.62	12728.38	14495.90	14124.50	13694.40
La	148.80	142.30	132.24	136.80	148.60	158.50	144.70
Ce	270.80	262.60	245.89	248.14	270.60	284.90	262.80
Pr	31.28	30.44	28.75	28.65	31.61	32.89	30.15
Nd	116.70	117.30	110.78	111.01	119.40	123.20	113.60
Sm	21.14	21.39	21.53	21.12	21.03	22.10	20.38
Eu	5.19	5.16	6.52	6.83	4.88	5.11	4.60
Gd	16.28	15.82	14.46	14.93	15.91	16.48	15.26
Tb	1.85	1.77	1.77	1.78	1.77	1.90	1.70
Dy	8.01	7.85	8.00	7.88	7.78	8.37	7.44
Ho	1.26	1.21	1.28	1.28	1.20	1.30	1.17
Er	2.90	2.87	3.04	2.98	2.87	3.13	2.74
Tm	0.35	0.35	0.38	0.36	0.36	0.38	0.33
Yb	2.15	2.15	2.13	2.13	2.18	2.28	2.06
Lu	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.30	0.31	0.33	0.29
Hf	6.50	6.62	6.32	6.66	6.69	6.79	6.44
Ta	0.55	0.59	0.55	0.54	0.63	0.62	0.52
Pb	277.50	134.90	147.78	294.62	280.90	295.10	276.00

Th	68.22	69.95	72.62	78.43	73.86	79.26	70.30
U	7.53	9.77	10.57	11.83	10.37	8.59	9.44
δEu	0.85	0.86	1.13	1.18	0.82	0.82	0.80
Sr-Nd-Pb-Hf-Zn isotopes							
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$	0.715930	0.715740	0.715798	0.715831	0.715742	0.715854	0.715880
2σ	0.000005	0.000008	0.000008	0.000006	0.000004	0.000006	0.000006
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}$	0.512044	0.512045	0.512035	0.512055	0.512046	0.512047	0.512042
2σ	0.000002	0.000004	0.000001	0.000002	0.000003	0.000003	0.000001
$^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$	0.282466	0.282475	0.282481	0.282475	0.282472	0.282474	0.282475
2σ	0.000006	0.000007	0.000005	0.000007	0.000007	0.000007	0.000006
$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	18.454	18.461	18.455	18.455	18.457	18.455	18.456
2σ	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	15.748	15.745	15.748	15.748	15.748	15.749	15.749
2σ	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}$	39.503	39.510	39.512	39.520	39.504	39.517	39.522
2σ	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
$\delta^{66}\text{Zn}$ (‰)	0.27	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.30	0.28
2σ	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.02
$\delta^{68}\text{Zn}$ (‰)	0.52	0.57	0.59	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.57
2σ	0.01	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.03
$^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}_{(i)}$	0.715844	0.715647	0.715704	0.715753	0.715689	0.715791	0.715822
$^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd}_{(t)}$	0.512032	0.512033	0.512023	0.512043	0.512034	0.512035	0.512030
$\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(t)}$	-11.4	-11.4	-11.6	-11.2	-11.4	-11.4	-11.5
$^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}_{(t)}$	0.282464	0.282473	0.282479	0.282473	0.282470	0.282472	0.282473
$\epsilon\text{Hf}_{(t)}$	-10.5	-10.2	-10.0	-10.2	-10.3	-10.3	-10.2

$\Delta\epsilon_{\text{Hf}(t)}$	6.0	6.2	6.8	5.9	6.1	6.1	6.3
$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}_{(i)}$	18.450	18.450	18.444	18.449	18.457	18.455	18.456
$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}_{(i)}$	15.748	15.745	15.747	15.748	15.748	15.749	15.749
$^{208}\text{Pb}/^{204}\text{Pb}_{(i)}$	39.489	39.482	39.486	39.505	39.504	39.517	39.522

Note: $\text{Mg\#} = \text{Mg}^{2+}/(\text{Mg}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{2+}) \times 100$; $\delta\text{Eu} = \text{Eu}_N / (\text{Sm}_N \times \text{Gd}_N)^{1/2}$. The initial Sr–Nd–Hf–Pb isotopic values of studied rocks were calculated using their eruption ages. The present chondrite has: $^{87}\text{Rb}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.0847$; $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.7045$; $^{147}\text{Sm}/^{144}\text{Nd} = 0.1967$, $^{143}\text{Nd}/^{144}\text{Nd} = 0.512638$, $^{176}\text{Lu}/^{177}\text{Hf} = 0.0332$, and $^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf} = 0.282772$. $\lambda_{\text{Rb}} = 1.42 \times 10^{-11} \text{ year}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{\text{Sm}} = 6.54 \times 10^{-12} \text{ year}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{\text{Lu}} = 1.867 \times 10^{-11} \text{ year}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{\text{U}238} = 0.155125 \times 10^{-9} \text{ year}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{\text{U}235} = 0.98485 \times 10^{-9} \text{ year}^{-1}$; and $\lambda_{\text{Th}232} = 0.049475 \times 10^{-9} \text{ year}^{-1}$. $\epsilon_{\text{Nd}(t)} = [({}^{143}\text{Nd}/{}^{144}\text{Nd})_S / ({}^{143}\text{Nd}/{}^{144}\text{Nd})_{\text{CHUR}} - 1] \times 10,000$. $\epsilon_{\text{Hf}(t)} = [({}^{176}\text{Hf}/{}^{177}\text{Hf})_S / ({}^{176}\text{Hf}/{}^{177}\text{Hf})_{\text{CHUR}} - 1] \times 10,000$. $\Delta\epsilon_{\text{Hf}(t)} = \epsilon_{\text{Hf}(t)} - 1.55\epsilon_{\text{Nd}(t)} - 1.21$ (Vervoort et al., 2011).

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